

Plastic-associated harmful phytoplankton assemblages in coastal and off-shore habitats of the Mediterranean Sea

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Abstract

Plastics (macro, micro and nanoplastics) are durable and persistent pollutants that may alter pelagic and coastal ecosystem functions. Plastics provide a durable substrate that can be colonized by micro and macro-organisms. They support the growth of potential pathogens and HAB species. Further, plastic debris has been considered to play a key role in the dispersal also of biotoxins. The present study aimed to investigate harmful phytoplankton assemblages that colonized numerous samples of micro and macro-plastics collected in the Mediterranean Sea by qPCR assays, and to forecast toxin dispersal by quantifying toxin content onto plastic debris. Further, the impact of polystyrene nanoparticles (PS NPs) to the HA diatom *Skeletonema marinoi* was analyzed. All plastic samples were positive for the presence of Dinophyceae and Bacillariophyceae communities and some plastic samples were colonized by toxic species of dinoflagellate *Alexandrium pacificum*, *Alexandrium minutum*, *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata* and diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. Strains of *A. pacificum* isolated from plastic debris and analyzed by LC-HRMS produced PST (paralytic shellfish toxins). The levels of potential toxins on plastic samples ranged from 10¹ to 10² ng cm⁻². The interactions between HA diatom and plastic nanoparticles demonstrated an increase of both extracellular and intracellular reactive oxygen species, and significantly reduced colonies length using TEM and SEM techniques. Then, plastics can negatively impact the ecological functioning of oceans. The potential risk of harmful microalgae dispersal associated with plastic pollution was illustrated as well as for chemical compounds to transfer through the trophic chain with implications for human health and marine ecosystem.

Keywords: Assemblages, dispersal, harmful algae, biotoxins, marine plastics, qPCR, ROS, adhesion

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Introduction

Amounts of 23,150 of the 268,940 tons of plastic particles floating on the surface of the world's oceans are found on the Mediterranean Sea surface. Floating plastics are a durable and persistent substratum for the bio-adhesion of micro- and macro-organisms enabling dispersal from native to new habitats (Eriksen *et al.*, 2014). Plastic debris has been considered to play a role in the dispersal of toxic compounds having implications for humans and marine organisms across the marine food web. In marine ecosystems, biological interactions between plastic debris and biota include biofouling that starts from the adsorption of organic molecules followed by the increased adhesion of bacteria, diatoms and other microorganism communities. Finally, these microorganisms are linked together in a biofilm by extracellular polymeric substances (Flemming and Wingender, 2010). In previous studies, the harmful dinoflagellates *Alexandrium* sp., *Coolia* sp. and *Ostreopsis* sp. were recorded on plastics floating in coastal waters of the Mediterranean Sea (Zettler *et al.*, 2013). Plastic fragmentation, due to degradation of larger plastic waste, down to nanoscale particles (from 1 to 100 nm) was also demonstrated (Corsi *et al.*, 2020) and the effects, such as adhesion, production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reduction of photosynthetic yield due to exposure of phytoplankton species to these particles has been documented (Bellingeri *et al.*, 2020). This study aims to characterize and quantify target harmful phytoplankton taxa potentially attached to numerous samples of micro and macro -plastics collected in the coastal waters and offshore of the Mediterranean Sea by the quantitative PCR assay. The levels of potential

toxins transported by plastic samples were determined and the impact of polystyrene nanoparticles (PS NPs) on *Skeletonema marinoi* including ROS production, effects on algal growth and colony length was investigated.

Material and Methods

Environmental plastic sampling and processing

A total of 42 plastic samples were collected in different areas of the Mediterranean Sea from March 2016 to May 2017. Sampling was done by the use of a manta net of 330 µm mesh size, and manually. These macro and micro -plastic samples were analyzed by qPCR for molecular abundance quantification of attached microalgal taxa. Moreover, pellets obtained from ten *A. pacificum* strains isolated from plastic samples were analyzed for PST content by liquid chromatography-high resolution multiple stage mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS). Cultures of the diatom *S. marinoi* CBA4 was used for nanoplastic effects determination.

FTIR spectroscopy

A Nicolet 6700 FT-IR spectrometer (Thermo Fisher, U.S.A.) fitted with a single bounce attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory was used to characterize the plastic samples.

DNA extraction and qPCR analyses on environmental marine plastic samples

The genomic DNA was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), according to the manufacturer's instructions. For the quantification of Dinophyceae, Bacillariophyceae, *A.*

minutum, *A. pacificum*, *O. cf. ovata* and *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. in plastic samples, different standard curves were used (see also Casabianca *et al.*, 2019).

Adhesion rate of harmful algal species to the plastic substrate

Strains of *P. multistriata* CBA174, *Skeletonema marinoi* CBA4, *A. minutum* CBA57, *A. pacificum* CNR-SRA4, *L. polyedrum* LPA0510, *P. reticulatum* PRA0311, *G. spinifera* CBA5 and *O. cf. ovata* CBA1291 were grown in glass bottles together with sterilized plastic sheets. A plastic sheet was harvested every four days from the inoculum and gently scraped in sterile seawater in order to recover the cells adhering to the plastic sheets. Subsamples of 1 mL were collected for cell density estimation by light microscopy. The adhesion rates was determined using the equation: $\mu = \ln(Nt/N0)/\Delta t$, where N is the number of the plastic adherent cells expressed as cells cm⁻² and Δt is the time interval expressed in days.

S. marinoi-PS

NPs interaction and quantification of ROS

S. marinoi cultures were exposed to 1, 10, 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ PS NPs for 15 days and cells growth was investigated. The physical interaction between algal cells and nanoplastics was imaged through ESEM and TEM.

The production of ROS was measured by following the conversion of the non-fluorescent dihydrodichlorofluorescein diacetate (H₂DCF-DA) to the highly fluorescent compound 2', 7',-dichlorofluorescein (DCF) (see Bellingeri *et al.*, 2020).

Results and Discussion

The proportion of sampled microplastics was 64% non-polar (polyethylene and polypropylene) and 36% had a certain level of polarity. All the 42 plastic samples tested positive for the presence of Dinophyceae and Bacillariophyceae and by the qPCR quantification of harmful target microalgal taxa, sixteen plastic samples showed the presence of the toxic and allochthonous *A. pacificum*, nine samples tested positive for the presence of *A. minutum* and *O. cf. ovata* and *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. was present in almost all plastic samples (n = 31) (Fig. 1). The abundance of the phytoplankton communities found on environmental plastics surface was highly variable with Bacillariophyceae showing the highest abundance of cells, probably because they can the most easily form biofilms on plastics by producing extracellular substances (Reisser *et al.*, 2014). Dinophyceae showed lower abundance than Bacillariophyceae on field marine plastics, but *in vitro* experiments demonstrated that *A. pacificum*, *A. minutum* and *O. cf. ovata* were able to attach to the environmental plastics. Indeed, the dinoflagellate *A. pacificum* appeared to be the species that adhered to the plastics the most rapidly, followed by the diatoms *S. marinoi* and *P. multistriata*. The species that adhered at the slowest rate were *A. minutum* and *O. cf. ovata* (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Molecular quantification of target harmful microalgal species abundance on plastics collected in the Mediterranean Sea by qPCR assay. (A) *Alexandrium pacificum*, (B) *A. minutum*, (C) *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*, (D) *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp.

Thus, from these results and using a qPCR approach we demonstrated that some target HA species adhere tightly to floating plastic debris, which suggests that the selected harmful microalgal species could potentially spread through marine ecosystems and trophic chain, negatively impacting human health and environment.

Fig. 2. Adhesion rates of different cultured harmful microalgal strains to the plastic surfaces (means \pm SD, n = 3). *Alexandrium pacificum* (■), *Skeletonema marinoi* (Δ), *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* (\blacktriangle), *Alexandrium minutum* (\blacklozenge) and *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* (\bullet).

Moreover, all the 10 tested strains of *A. pacificum* produced PST, with total toxin content in the range from 35.14 to 6,032 fg cell⁻¹. From this study, we conclude that the PSP producing species can transport 1-72 pg cm⁻² of PST. Considering the other target species we hypothesized that *Pseudo-nitzschia* can potentially contribute to domoic acid transport with values in the range of 5 and 443 ng cm⁻² on floating plastics based

on the literature values (Trainer *et al.*, 2012). Based on the maximum abundance of 259 cells cm^{-2} of *O. cf. ovata* found on the plastics, we conclude that at least 1-62 ng PLTX compounds cm^{-2} must be accumulated in floating plastics debris (Tartaglione *et al.*, 2017). Marine plastic debris can be linked to a mixture of marine biotoxins, produced by microalgae which can be transferred throughout the trophic chain to higher trophic levels, and thus contaminate seafood for humans (Casabianca *et al.*, 2019).

No effects on diatom growth were observed upon exposure to PS NPs (1, 10 and 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 15 days (Kruskal-Wallis Hc = 0.63, p = 0.89). TEM images clearly show nanoplastic aggregates mainly interacting with the terminal fulcportula processes (TFPP) of *S. marinoi* (Figs. 3 a, b). This adhesion affected the length of *S. marinoi* chains.

PS NPs exposed algae showed a high percentage of single cells and 2-cell chains, altogether accounting for 95% and 84% of those exposed to 10 and 50 mg/mL, respectively. Moreover, the occurrence of contact-induced stress, following cell-PS NPs interactions, resulted in enhanced production of both intracellular and extracellular ROS (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. TEM images of *S. marinoi* exposed to PS NPs.

From these results, new information was obtained regarding the quantities of harmful marine species attached to the plastics floating in the Mediterranean Sea based on qPCR assays. These findings illustrate the potential risk of harmful microorganism dispersal associated with plastic pollution. HA dinoflagellate species abundance was found to be lower than that of diatom communities which include potentially toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. Moreover, the potential risk of transport of toxins by plastic debris could be likely.

Fig. 4. Intracellular and extracellular ROS levels in *S. marinoi* exposed to PS NPs (1, 10, 50 $\mu\text{g PS mL}^{-1}$) and in controls. Data shown as fluorescence units/cell density (cells mL^{-1}). Data with different letters are statistically different with $p < 0.005$.

By the exposure to plastic nanoparticles, no lethal effect to the marine diatom *S. marinoi* was observed, while an increase in intracellular and extracellular oxidative stress and a reduction of diatom's chain length were observed. These effects could have potential ecological implications such as changes in algal buoyancy as well as the formation and sinking of aggregates potentially affecting marine carbon pump. From the evidence we have shown, measures for preventing and managing plastic pollution are needed

but also further investigation should be carried out to predict the ecological impacts on phytoplankton assemblages involved in primary production.

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